

LINGO-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'zbek va ingliz maqollarini o'z ichiga oladi. Har bir xalqning maqollari o'z tarixiga qarab bir-biridan yaratilish va odamlarni turmush tarzlarida ifodalanish usullari orqali farqlanadi. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz maqollarining qiyosiy tahlili va lingvo-kulturologik xususiyatlari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqollar, tarjima, ekvivalent, lingvo-kulturologik xususiyatlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются разные пословицы узбекского и английского языков. В каждом языке есть свой запас пословиц, а пословицы на одном языке сегодня отражают все века и времена. Пословицы представляют нас как наблюдение повседневной жизни, составляют популярную философию жизни и дают представление о человеческом поведении и характере. В данной статье рассматриваются сравнительный анализ узбекских и английских пословиц, трансформации, использованные при переводе узбекских народных пословиц на английский язык, и их лингво-культурологические особенности.

Ключевые слова: Пословицы, поговорки, перевод, эквивалент, лингво-культурологические особенности.

The proverbs of each people are created from each other depending on their history distinguished by the ways in which people are represented in their lifestyles. Proverbs analyzed through:

Morphological

Lexicon

Etiological Stylistics methods. Through analyses we can see the clear differences between Uzbek and

English proverbs. One of the first differences between them is the images used in proverbs. Animals are often used in English proverbs as a symbol to express human nature.

For example: - Eagles do not catch flies.

- The higher the monkey climbs the more he shows his tail.

In contrast, Uzbek proverbs describe the simple life of a person without using animals.

For example: O'xshatmasdan uchratmas.

Here we must mention the changes of a few examples of proverbs translating from one language to another. The English equivalent form of the Uzbek proverb given above:

- O'xshatmasdan uchratmas (They do not meet if they do not look like each

other) – Birds of a feather flock together.

There are several ways available to translate proverbs from one language to another:

Using a phraseological equivalent;

Absolute equivalent

A similar equivalent

Using direct translation.

There are the same English and Uzbek proverbs that can be translated by using absolute equivalent

For example: 1. A watched pot never boils. – Kutilgan qozon qaynamas.

Wisdom is the beauty of men – Odam bezagi – aql.

Manners make the man – Insonni fazilatlar ulug'laydi.

There are some types of Uzbek proverbs that are not directly translatable into English. In this case, we will have to find the proverbs in English language then translate into it.

For example: - Tirriq qo'zi podani buzar (Thin lamb spoils the herd) - A rotten apple spoils the barrel.

- O'z uying – o'lan to'shaging – East or west, home is best

The English proverb "rotten apple" means "a bad person", but this meaning in Uzbek proverb is given like "skinny lambs spoil the herd".

There is some lexis that does not exist in English language, so some proverbs are translated into English by explanation.

For example, there is an Uzbek proverb that represents the entrepreneurship, wisdom and ingenuity of women. It is translated as:

Erni er qiladigan ham, qaro yer qiladigan ham xotin.

Meaning: A good wife makes a good husband, a bad woman makes a bad husband.

Language is the culture, values and beliefs of each nation, in general it is the most important factor in expressing the unique aspects of the nation.

List of used literature:

1. Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek And English Proverbs –

Ahmedov Umidjon Lecturer Of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

2. Linguistic and cultural studies of English and Uzbek proverbs

semantic features – written for the Master's academic degree dissertation - Akhmedova Ugiljon Kuronboyevna